
EFFECTIVENESS OF UTILIZATION OF CLASS II BITUNG PPLP RESOURCES IN IMPLEMENTING MARITIME SAFETY

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to analyze the effectiveness of the utilization of PPLP Class II Bitung resources in implementing maritime safety. The research method used is a qualitative approach with data collection techniques through in-depth interviews, observation, and documentation. Research informants consisted of structural officials, operational officers, and administrative staff directly involved in the implementation of maritime safety tasks. Data analysis was carried out through data reduction, data presentation, and systematic drawing of conclusions. The results of the study indicate that the effectiveness of resource utilization is not yet fully optimal. From the human resources aspect, there are limitations in numbers and competencies that are not evenly distributed. From the aspect of facilities and infrastructure, there are still limitations in numbers and conditions that are not optimal. From the budget aspect, limited allocations and administrative constraints affect operational implementation. Supporting factors include human resource commitment and inter-agency cooperation, while inhibiting factors include limited resources and complex bureaucracy. The conclusion of this study indicates that the effectiveness of resource utilization is influenced by the alignment between organizational capacity and operational demands. The implications of this study emphasize the need to improve human resources, strengthen facilities, optimize budgets, and improve managerial and coordination systems.

Keywords: organizational effectiveness, resources, maritime safety, PPLP

INTRODUCTION

PPLP is a technical implementation unit under the Directorate General of Sea Transportation, Ministry of Transportation, mandated to carry out maritime guarding and patrolling duties, enforce certain laws at sea, prevent maritime accidents, coordinate initial search and rescue (SAR), and supervise the implementation of maritime safety regulations. This institution not only functions as a public service hub, but also as a state instrument in creating a safe, orderly maritime space, and is protected from potential risks of accidents, violations of the law, or threats to the safety of life at sea. This mandate is expressly regulated in the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation Number PM 59 of 2018 concerning the Implementation of Sea and Coast Guard, which places PPLP as the front guard in mitigating maritime risks. However, the implementation of this strategic mandate is highly dependent on the effective utilization of the organization's resources. From a public administration perspective, organizational effectiveness cannot be separated from the institution's ability to optimally manage resources. Quoting the views of HNS Tangkilisan (2015), an academic and Public Administration expert from Manado State University (Unima), the effectiveness of a public organization is largely determined by the extent to which management is able to integrate human resources, infrastructure, and budgets to achieve predetermined service objectives, amidst the limitations and dynamics of the external environment. If resource management is ineffective, there will be a gap between the regulatory mandate and the reality of performance on the ground. Issues related to the sustainability and effectiveness of resource utilization in government institutions have become increasingly prominent concerns, in line with the push for bureaucratic reform that emphasizes performance optimization. As stated by Dwiyanto (2017), one of the root causes of the low quality of public services in Indonesia is

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ineffective resource management, which includes incompetent human resources, inadequate facilities, and organizational mechanisms that are not adaptive to the dynamics of community needs. This condition has the potential to also occur in the maritime safety sector, including the operations of the Class II Bitung PPLP. Based on initial documentation and mapping of conditions at the research site, several crucial phenomena indicate ineffective resource utilization. First, regarding Human Resources (HR). Documentation of the number of HR personnel at the research site reveals a significant disparity between the number of available personnel and the size of the work area and the operational burden they must bear. The Bitung Class II PPLP has a surveillance area encompassing extensive waters with high traffic volumes of merchant vessels, fishing vessels, and passenger ships. However, the number of operational personnel, particularly patrol boat crews and technical officers, often does not match the ideal requirement. This phenomenon forces multiple roles, where one personnel must handle both operational and administrative functions. This has the potential to reduce concentration, increase fatigue, and ultimately reduce the effectiveness of safety patrols. Furthermore, in terms of quality, despite the high dedication of the existing HR, there are still competency gaps in operating modern maritime technology and handling complex emergency situations, which require ongoing training that has not been fully accommodated.

Second, and a crucial primary focus, is the condition of facilities and infrastructure. The effectiveness of maritime security depends heavily on the seaworthiness of vessels and the sophistication of their supporting equipment. At the Bitung Class II PPLP, the primary facility, the State Patrol Vessel (KN), is a vital asset. However, initial observations indicate that several patrol vessels have reached a relatively advanced age, resulting in an increased frequency of technical breakdowns. This situation is exacerbated by maintenance cycles that are often hampered by budget constraints and lengthy spare parts procurement procedures. When patrol vessels are not on standby or operational readiness, the maritime surveillance coverage automatically narrows, leaving a blind spot in monitoring shipping safety.

In addition to ships, supporting infrastructure such as navigation equipment (Radar, GPS, Automatic Identification System/AIS), communication systems (VHF/HF Radio), and safety equipment (lifesaving appliances) also face challenges. The development of global maritime technology demands state-of-the-art equipment standards for early detection and rapid response. However, the reality on the ground shows that some equipment is still conventional or has experienced functional decline. As emphasized by Lubis (2019) in his research on the effectiveness of shipping safety supervision, maritime technology facilities that are not updated or periodically maintained will drastically reduce the ability to detect early and respond quickly to safety incidents, leading to an increased risk of maritime accidents. Therefore, focusing on the infrastructure aspect in this research is very urgent and requires in-depth analysis.

Third, the budgeting aspect. Patrol vessels require significant operational costs, ranging from fuel and engine maintenance to spare parts replacement and crew logistical support. When the budget is limited or not allocated proportionally and timely, patrol and safety operations will be less intense. Within the framework of public administration, this reflects a classic problem referred to by Mahmudi (2019) as inefficiency due to budget constraints, where organizational performance depends not solely on the size of the budget ceiling, but on how effectively the budget is managed, prioritized, and absorbed. Delays in budget disbursement or a mismatch between budget planning and actual needs in the field often force organizations to postpone preventive maintenance activities, which ultimately triggers more severe damage and higher repair costs.

Fourth, the management and coordination system. The Bitung PPLP does not operate in a vacuum. This institution interacts intensively with various institutions, such as the Harbormaster and Port Authority Office (KSOP), the National Search and Rescue Agency (BASARNAS), the Indonesian Navy, and the Maritime Police (Polairud). Disorganized coordination and collaboration often lead to overlapping functions, slow communication, or uncoordinated responses when incidents occur at sea. As emphasized by Keban (2014), the effectiveness of public organizations is greatly influenced by their ability to collaborate, particularly in sectors that require collective work across institutions. The multidimensional nature of maritime safety requires information integration, role alignment, and resource synergy between agencies. If the PPLP's internal management system is not fully adaptive and flexible in responding to field dynamics, external coordination will be hampered.

From a regulatory perspective, maritime safety in Indonesia is governed by various robust legal instruments, including Law No. 17 of 2008 concerning Shipping. However, the implementation of these regulations is highly dependent on the readiness of the implementing unit's resources. When regulations are implemented faster than the operational readiness of the implementing unit in the field, a gap will arise between the expected service standards (policy) and the organization's actual ability to implement them (implementation gap). This phenomenon aligns with Sedarmayanti's (2017) view that public bureaucracies often face policy implementation challenges when resources are

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inadequate to effectively implement regulations. Based on the description of the problems above, it is very important to explicitly explain what is being researched in this study. This study does not only aim to describe the general condition of PPLP Class II Bitung, but also specifically examines the effectiveness of resource utilization consisting of four main dimensions: (1) Utilization of Human Resources (HR) in terms of quantity, quality, and distribution of workload; (2) Utilization of Facilities and Infrastructure, with a deep focus on the seaworthiness of patrol vessels, the sophistication of navigation equipment, and maintenance systems; (3) Utilization of Budget in supporting operations and maintenance; and (4) Effectiveness of Managerial and Coordination Systems, both internal and external. In addition, this study will also identify and analyze supporting and inhibiting factors that influence the effectiveness of resource utilization in implementing maritime safety.

METHOD

This research uses a qualitative approach with a case study design. The qualitative approach was chosen because the research objective was to deeply understand the meaning, process, and social context of the implementation of the People's Business Credit (KUR) policy in Bitung City. As stated by Creswell and Poth (2023), a qualitative approach allows researchers to act as the primary instrument in data collection and interpretation, thereby capturing dynamics that cannot be measured quantitatively. The case study design was chosen because this research focuses on a specific spatial and policy context, namely the implementation of Regulation of the Coordinating Minister for Economic Affairs Number 7 of 2024 concerning People's Business Credit in Bitung City and its impact on the performance of MSMEs as the target group. This approach aligns with the characteristics of public administration research, which emphasizes understanding empirical realities on the ground (Moleong, 2021; Yin, 2018). The research location and site were determined in Bitung City, North Sulawesi Province, with coverage including BRI Bitung Unit and Branch Offices, the Bitung City Cooperative and MSME Office, and the business locations of MSMEs receiving KUR spread across Girian, Maesa, and Aertembaga Districts. Research informants were determined by *purposive sampling* and *snowball sampling*, grouped based on role and depth of experience. The first group were KUR disbursement officials/implementers from BRI Bitung (Head of Unit, Head of Micro RM, and KUR Mantri) with a minimum of 2 years of experience handling KUR. The second group were officials from the Bitung City Cooperative & MSME Office (Head of MSME Division and accompanying staff).

The third group were MSMEs receiving KUR selected stratified based on ceiling level (Super Micro ≤ 10 million, Micro ≤ 100 million, Small $>100-500$ million), business sector, and performance trends. The addition of informants was carried out using a *snowball method* until the data saturation point was reached (Sugiyono, 2022). Data collection techniques were carried out in three ways. First, semi-structured *in-depth interviews* using an interview guide to gather information from informants. Second, field observations of the operational process of KUR distribution and MSME business activities. Third, documentation of KUR realization reports, laws and regulations, photos, and other supporting data. Research indicators are described in two main focuses. The first focus is the technical distribution of KUR according to Coordinating Ministerial Regulation No. 7 of 2024, which is broken down into four sub-indicators: (1) Business Criteria (business feasibility and debtor *bankable status*); (2) Credit History (verification mechanisms through SLIK OJK and SIKP); (3) Requirements and Documents (administrative completeness such as NIB, NPWP, business certificate); and (4) KUR Types and Ceilings (understanding of Super Micro, Micro, and Small schemes). The second focus is on the determinant factors in the KUR distribution process that impact MSME performance, including the rigidity of the SLIK system, top-up administrative delays, the availability of PLUT assistance, and public financial literacy.

Data analysis used an interactive model from Miles, Huberman, and Saldaña (2014), which consists of four stages: *data collection* (data collection through interviews, observation, and documentation); *data condensation* (data selection, focusing, simplification, and transformation); *data display* (data presentation in narrative text and tables); and *conclusion drawing/verification*. Analysis was carried out continuously from before entering the field until after the research was completed. Data validity was guaranteed through four criteria: *credibility* (internal validity) through triangulation of sources, techniques, and time, as well as *member checks*; *transferability* (external validity) by providing detailed contextual descriptions; *dependability* (reliability) through audits of the entire research process; and *confirmability* (objectivity) by conducting *audit trials* to ensure findings align with field data (Moleong, 2021). With this method, the research is expected to comprehensively answer the problem formulation and produce policy recommendations based on empirical evidence.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Effectiveness of utilization of PPLP Class II Bitung resources in implementing maritime safety

a. Utilization of Human Resources (HR)

Human resource (HR) utilization is a key factor in determining organizational effectiveness, particularly in maritime safety implementation at the Class II Bitung PPLP. Research has shown that HR utilization is not yet fully optimal, although it is generally sufficient to support operational tasks. However, from a human resource quantity perspective, this study indicates a limited number of personnel that is disproportionate to the size of the work area and operational load. This condition results in duplication of duties and an imbalance in the workload. From Steers' perspective, this condition indicates that the organization has not been able to match resource capacity to the demands of the work environment, thus impacting organizational effectiveness (Steers, 1985). This is also supported by previous research showing that human resource shortages in public organizations can reduce service quality and work effectiveness (Mahmudi, 2015:89).

In terms of human resource quality, research results indicate that personnel's technical competence is sufficient to perform routine tasks, but there are still limitations in mastering technology and handling emergency situations. This indicates that human resource development is not yet fully optimal. In public sector human resource management theory, competency development is a crucial factor in increasing organizational effectiveness (Armstrong, 2014:112). Furthermore, according to Hasibuan (2016:67), ongoing training is necessary to improve employee capabilities in dealing with changes in the work environment. Research findings also indicate that HR training has not been implemented evenly and sustainably, resulting in competency gaps among personnel. From Steers' perspective, this condition is related to management policies and practices that do not fully support HR capacity building. This also aligns with previous research that suggests a lack of training is a factor inhibiting the effectiveness of public sector organizations (Sutrisno, 2019:134). Furthermore, from a work motivation perspective, research results indicate that human resources at PPLP Class II Bitung have high work motivation, driven by a sense of responsibility for maritime safety. This is a key contributing factor to the effectiveness of human resource utilization. According to Mangkunegara (2017:94), high work motivation can improve employee performance, even under conditions of limited resources.

However, this work motivation is not fully supported by optimal working conditions, such as limited facilities, budgets, and high workloads. In organizational effectiveness theory, this condition indicates an imbalance between individual and organizational factors, which can affect overall effectiveness (Steers, 1985). In terms of human resource performance, research results show that personnel performance is quite good in carrying out their duties, but not optimal due to various limitations. This indicates that the effectiveness of human resource utilization has not been fully achieved. In this context, effectiveness is not only measured by individual abilities, but also by the support of the organizational system as a whole (Mahmudi, 2015:102). This finding is also supported by previous research showing that the effectiveness of public organizations is greatly influenced by the quality and quantity of human resources, as well as adequate management support (Wibowo, 2018:76). Other research also states that an imbalance between workload and the number of human resources can reduce the effectiveness of public services (Suryani, 2020:58).

Thus, based on the analysis using Steers theory and HR management theory, it can be concluded that the effectiveness of HR utilization in PPLP Class II Bitung is influenced by several main factors, namely: Limited number of HR, which causes high workload and multiple tasks, Uneven quality of HR, especially in mastering technology and handling emergency situations, Training that is not optimal, both in terms of frequency and equality. High work motivation, as the main supporting factor. As well as HR performance that is quite good, but not optimal due to limitations in the support system.

b. Utilization of Facilities and Infrastructure

The utilization of facilities and infrastructure is a fundamental element in determining the effectiveness of public organizations, particularly in the context of maritime safety implementation at the Class II Bitung PPLP. The research found that the available facilities and infrastructure have been utilized to support operational activities, but their utilization has not been fully optimized due to various limitations. From the perspective of Steers' Organizational Effectiveness Theory, organizational effectiveness is influenced by the alignment of organizational resources with environmental demands and the desired goals (Steers, 1985). Facilities and infrastructure, in this case, are part of the organization's characteristics, which serve as the main input in carrying out operational activities. Research findings indicate that PPLP Class II Bitung already has primary facilities such as patrol boats, navigation tools (GPS, radar),

communication systems (radio), and safety equipment (life jackets and emergency equipment). The existence of these facilities indicates that the organization structurally has basic facility support. However, in terms of facility adequacy, there is a mismatch between the number of available facilities and operational needs. The vast working area and high shipping intensity require the availability of more and more modern facilities. This condition limits the scope of patrols and surveillance. In Steers' theory, a mismatch between organizational capacity and environmental demands will reduce the level of organizational effectiveness (Steers, 1985). This aligns with Mahmudi's (2015:123) opinion that limited facilities in public organizations can hinder the achievement of optimal performance.

In terms of facility condition, research results indicate that some facilities are still operational, but not fully optimal. The decline in facility condition, particularly patrol boats and technical equipment, is due to the facility's age and high intensity of use. This condition has resulted in decreased operational performance and increased work risks. According to Mardiasmo (2018:156), poorly maintained assets will reduce the effectiveness of public services and increase the potential for operational losses. Furthermore, from a maintenance and upkeep perspective, research indicates that maintenance activities have been carried out, but have not been optimal. Budget constraints and lengthy administrative processes are the main obstacles to maintenance implementation. As a result, some facilities continue to be used even though they are not in optimal condition. In public asset management theory, ongoing maintenance is a crucial factor in maintaining the function and utility of assets (Siregar, 2017:88). Ineffective maintenance indicates weaknesses in the organization's asset management.

From a technological perspective, it was found that some facilities have not fully kept pace with developments in modern maritime technology. This impacts operational efficiency and effectiveness, particularly in navigation and communications. According to Dwiyanto (2014:102), the use of technology in public organizations plays a significant role in improving service quality and work effectiveness. Furthermore, from the perspective of constraints on the use of facilities, various obstacles were found, such as technical problems, limited number of facilities, and communication system constraints. This indicates that although facilities are available, their utilization is not yet optimal. From an organizational effectiveness perspective, this condition indicates an imbalance between input (facilities) and output (performance), which has an impact on decreased effectiveness (Steers, 1985).

In terms of operational impact, the condition of facilities significantly impacts the effectiveness of patrols and surveillance. Facilities in good condition enable optimal patrols, expand surveillance coverage, and accelerate response times to maritime incidents. Conversely, suboptimal facilities can lead to limitations in task execution, delayed responses, and increased safety risks. This demonstrates that facilities and infrastructure are crucial factors in the effectiveness of maritime safety implementation. This finding is also supported by previous research, which states that the availability and condition of infrastructure directly impact the effectiveness of public organizations (Wibowo, 2018:92). Other research also shows that limited facilities can hinder task implementation and reduce service quality (Suryani, 2020:63). Overall, the effectiveness of facilities and infrastructure utilization at the Bitung Class II PPLP is not yet fully optimal, as there is still a gap between the condition of available facilities and operational needs. Therefore, improvements in facility procurement, maintenance systems, and the use of modern technology are needed to support more effective maritime safety implementation.

c. Budget Utilization

Budget utilization is a crucial component in determining the effectiveness of public organizations, particularly in implementing maritime safety at the Class II Bitung PPLP. The budget serves not only as a financing tool but also as an instrument for controlling and planning operational activities. The research found that budget utilization supported task implementation, but was not yet fully optimal in meeting overall operational needs. From the perspective of Steers' Organizational Effectiveness Theory, organizational effectiveness is largely determined by the organization's ability to manage resources efficiently and in accordance with organizational goals (Steers, 1985). In this case, the budget is part of the organization's characteristics, which plays a key role in supporting operational activities. Research findings indicate that the available budget at PPLP Class II Bitung has been allocated for various activities, such as sea patrols, facility maintenance, and human resource capacity building. This indicates that structurally, the budget has been used in accordance with its primary function. However, from the aspect of budget adequacy, research shows that the available budget is not fully sufficient for operational needs. Budget limitations force organizations to prioritize their activities, so that not all programs can be implemented optimally. From Steers' perspective, this condition indicates an imbalance between available resources and environmental demands, which has an impact on decreasing organizational effectiveness

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(Steers, 1985). This is in line with Mahmudi's opinion (2015:145), which states that budget limitations are one of the main obstacles in managing public sector organizations. From a budget allocation perspective, research results indicate that budget allocation has been based on priority needs, but not yet fully based on a comprehensive needs analysis. This results in a mismatch between budget allocation and actual needs on the ground. According to Mardiasmo (2018:178), inappropriate budget allocation can reduce budget effectiveness and organizational performance. Furthermore, from the budget utilization perspective, it was found that the budget had been used to support core operational activities, such as patrols and facility maintenance. However, budget constraints prevented optimal patrol and maintenance frequency. In public finance theory, effective budget use must produce optimal outputs and outcomes in line with organizational goals (Mahmudi, 2015:152).

From the perspective of budget administration processes, research shows that there are obstacles in the disbursement and use of budgets, which tend to take quite a long time. This lengthy bureaucratic process results in delays in operational activities. In the context of organizational effectiveness, delays in budget utilization indicate weaknesses in the managerial and administrative systems (Steers, 1985). This finding is also supported by previous research, which states that budget adequacy and management significantly influence the effectiveness of public sector organizations (Wibowo, 2018:101). Other research also shows that budget constraints can hamper program implementation and reduce the quality of public services (Suryani, 2020:70).

Overall, the effectiveness of budget utilization at the Class II Bitung PPLP is not yet fully optimal, as there is still a gap between budget availability and operational needs. Therefore, increased budget allocation, improvements to the financial planning and management system, and accelerated administrative processes are needed to support more effective maritime safety implementation.

2. Factors that influence the effectiveness of the utilization of Bitung Class II PPLP resources in implementing maritime safety

a. Supporting Factors

Supporting factors are crucial elements that contribute to an organization's success in effectively achieving its goals. In the context of PPLP Class II Bitung, supporting factors act as a force that enables optimal resource utilization in maritime safety management. The research findings revealed several factors that significantly support the effectiveness of resource utilization, both internally and externally. From the perspective of Steers' Organizational Effectiveness Theory, organizational effectiveness is influenced by the fit between organizational characteristics, environmental characteristics, employee characteristics, and management policies and practices (Steers, 1985). Supporting factors in this study indicate the existence of positive elements that strengthen the relationship between resources and the achievement of organizational goals. Furthermore, from the perspective of Edwards III's Policy Implementation Theory, successful policy implementation is influenced by four main variables: communication, resources, disposition, and bureaucratic structure (Edwards III, 1980). The supporting factors found in this study can be analyzed through these four variables. From a human resources (HR) perspective, research results indicate that employee commitment, dedication, and work experience are key factors supporting organizational effectiveness. Highly experienced and responsible employees are able to perform their duties optimally, even under limited resources. From Steers' perspective, good employee characteristics are crucial for improving organizational effectiveness (Steers, 1985). This aligns with Mangkunegara's (2017:94) opinion, which states that high work motivation and commitment can improve employee performance.

From a managerial perspective, the existence of a structured planning and task allocation system is a supporting factor in implementing activities. Although not yet fully optimal, the existing management system is capable of directing task execution in an organized manner. In public management theory, sound planning is fundamental to achieving organizational effectiveness (Dwiyanto, 2014:118). From a coordination perspective, cooperation between units and coordination with other agencies such as the KSOP, BASARNAS, TNI AL, and Polairud are crucial factors in supporting the implementation of maritime safety tasks. This coordination allows for synergy in activity implementation, particularly in emergency situations. From Edwards III's perspective, effective communication and coordination are key factors in successful policy implementation (Edwards III, 1980). From a policy and institutional support perspective, the existence of government policies that support maritime safety is a supporting factor in carrying out tasks. These policies provide the legal basis and direction for implementing organizational activities. According to Mardiasmo (2018:185), policy support is a crucial factor in increasing the effectiveness of public organizations.

From an organizational experience perspective, experience in carrying out operational tasks is a factor that supports effectiveness. This experience allows the organization to better understand field conditions and make informed decisions. This aligns with previous research that suggests organizational experience can increase the effectiveness of task execution (Wibowo, 2018:120). In terms of impact on effectiveness, these supporting factors play a role in enhancing an organization's ability to optimally utilize resources. Human resource commitment, managerial systems, coordination, and policy support enable organizations to continue carrying out their duties even under limited conditions. This finding is also supported by previous research showing that the effectiveness of public organizations is influenced by the quality of human resources, management systems, and good coordination (Suryani, 2020:80). Other research also states that cooperation and institutional support are important factors in increasing organizational effectiveness (Wibowo, 2018:125). Overall, these supporting factors indicate that the Bitung Class II PPLP has considerable potential to support effective resource utilization. However, to achieve optimal effectiveness, these supporting factors need to be balanced with efforts to address various remaining inhibiting factors.

b. Inhibiting Factors

Inhibiting factors are important variables that determine the effectiveness of resource utilization in public organizations. In the context of PPLP Class II Bitung, inhibiting factors act as obstacles that affect the optimal implementation of maritime safety tasks. The research found that effective resource utilization still faces various structural, managerial, and operational barriers. From the perspective of Steers' Organizational Effectiveness Theory, organizational effectiveness is influenced by the fit between organizational resources and environmental demands and management's ability to manage those resources (Steers, 1985). The inhibiting factors in this study indicate an imbalance between organizational capacity and operational demands, which results in a decline in organizational effectiveness.

Furthermore, from the perspective of Edwards III's Policy Implementation Theory, successful implementation is influenced by four main variables: communication, resources, disposition, and bureaucratic structure (Edwards III, 1980). The inhibiting factors found in this study can be analyzed based on these four variables. From a resource perspective, research findings indicate that limited human resources, infrastructure, and budget are key constraints on effective resource utilization. Limited human resources lead to high workloads and overlapping tasks, while limited facilities hamper patrol and oversight. Budgetary constraints also impact suboptimal operational activities. According to Edwards III, limited resources directly hinder policy implementation (Edwards III, 1980). This finding aligns with Mahmudi's (2015:145) assertion that limited resources are a key constraint in public sector organizations. From a communication perspective, research shows that internal and external coordination is not yet optimal. Delays in information delivery, limited communication facilities, and a lack of synchronization between units and agencies hinder task implementation. According to Edwards III's theory, ineffective communication can lead to errors in policy implementation (Edwards III, 1980). This is also supported by previous research showing that weak communication can reduce organizational effectiveness (Wibowo, 2018:110). From a bureaucratic structural perspective, it was found that lengthy administrative processes in budget management and procurement of facilities hamper operational activities. Complex procedures cause delays in decision-making and activity implementation. From Edwards III's perspective, an inefficient bureaucratic structure can hinder policy implementation (Edwards III, 1980). According to Mardiasmo (2018:178), a lengthy bureaucracy can reduce organizational efficiency and effectiveness.

From the dispositional aspect (the attitude of implementers), research results indicate that human resources generally have a high level of commitment and motivation in carrying out their duties. However, limited resources and suboptimal working conditions can affect work morale in the long term. According to Edwards III's theory, a positive disposition can support policy implementation, but it must be supported by adequate resources (Edwards III, 1980). Furthermore, from the perspective of Steers' Organizational Effectiveness Theory, inhibiting factors can also be seen from the mismatch between organizational characteristics and the environment. The dynamic operational environment of PPLP Class II Bitung, such as sea conditions, the size of the work area, and the intensity of shipping, demands high organizational capacity. However, limited resources mean the organization has not been able to fully adapt to these demands, thus impacting effectiveness. In terms of operational impact, these inhibiting factors directly impact the implementation of maritime safety tasks. Limited facilities and budgets lead to reduced patrol frequency, delays in facility maintenance, and limited human resource training. Suboptimal coordination also leads to delayed responses in handling incidents at sea. This demonstrates that inhibiting factors have a significant impact on organizational effectiveness.

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This finding is also supported by previous research, which states that the effectiveness of public organizations is significantly influenced by resource availability, communication quality, and bureaucratic efficiency (Suryani, 2020:75). Other research also indicates that resource constraints and ineffective coordination are key factors inhibiting organizational performance (Wibowo, 2018:115). Overall, these inhibiting factors indicate that the effective utilization of resources at the Class II Bitung PPLP is not yet fully optimal, as various obstacles still affect task implementation. Therefore, efforts are needed to improve resource management, enhance coordination, simplify bureaucracy, and strengthen the managerial system to support more effective maritime safety implementation.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion regarding the effectiveness of utilizing PPLP Class II Bitung resources in implementing maritime safety, several conclusions can be drawn as follows:

1. The level of effectiveness of resource utilization in PPLP Class II Bitung:
 - a. The effectiveness of human resource (HR) utilization is still suboptimal, despite the general high level of commitment, experience, and motivation. Limited personnel, an imbalanced workload, and uneven distribution of technical competencies are key factors impacting effectiveness. From Steers' perspective, this situation indicates a mismatch between HR capacity and the demands of the operational environment.
 - b. The effective utilization of facilities and infrastructure is not yet fully optimized, even though the main facilities are available and used in carrying out tasks. Limited facilities, suboptimal equipment condition, and inadequate maintenance are obstacles to operational support. This indicates a gap between organizational resources and field needs.
 - c. The effectiveness of budget utilization remains limited, with some being used to support operational activities but not yet meeting overall needs. Lengthy administrative processes and allocations that are not fully based on actual needs also impact budget effectiveness.
2. Factors that influence the effectiveness of the utilization of these resources in implementing maritime safety at PPLP Class II Bitung:
 - a. Factors supporting effectiveness include human resource commitment and experience, a structured management system, inter-unit and inter-agency coordination, and government policy support. These factors are key strengths in maintaining the continuity of task implementation despite limited resources.
 - b. Factors inhibiting effectiveness include limited human resources, facilities, and budget; suboptimal coordination; complex bureaucratic structures; and inflexible managerial systems. From Edwards III's perspective, these factors reflect constraints on resources, communication, and bureaucratic structure.

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